

Building a Shared Data Catalogue: User Research and Conceptual Considerations

Juliette Huygen^{1,2}, Maria Eskevich^{1,3}, Lotte Baltussen^{1,4}, and Bente Frissen^{1,5}

¹Huygens Institute, KNAW

²ORCID: 0009-0008-2359-3503

³ORCID: 0000-0002-1242-0753

⁴ORCID: 0009-0003-3961-4325

⁵ORCID: 0009-0002-5864-5306

1 Abstract

This presentation describes the steps taken at two Dutch institutes (Huygens¹ and Meertens² Institutes, KNAW) within the domains of the social sciences, humanities (SSH) and cultural heritage (CH) to develop a shared public-facing data catalogue. Nowadays, data-driven innovations and new digitization technologies make a deluge of complex and heterogeneous datasets available. We explore how we can make those more accessible for both our established and prospective audiences.

We focus on a user-centric perspective and will discuss (1) types of intended users, their expectations and behaviour profiles, (2) links between these perspectives and the technical requirements needed to combine greatly deviating types of sources within one portal and (3) domain specific considerations that shape our work. Moreover, we discuss the role our data catalogue design plays in allowing the sources to tell their stories both on the platform to closely fit the needs of the users, as well as to facilitate reuse in new projects.

2 Data deluge

Both within academic institutions and the cultural heritage field, ever growing amounts of digitally available material offer new possibilities for data-driven analysis and interdisciplinary research. Following the Dutch Digital Heritage Network³ guidelines, the heritage sector strives to make (digital) heritage Visible, Usable and Sustainable.(4)

¹ <https://huygens.knaw.nl/>

² <https://meertens.knaw.nl/>

³ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl>

However, while such efforts make CH collections digitally accessible to a wider audience, they often remain insufficiently documented and processed for researchers to use in their research. Conversely, research data as scientific output is still far from being considered a natural part of CH collections. Research project outputs become increasingly diversified, and many dissemination and impact plans now include and value the publishing of datasets and digital infrastructures.⁴ Moreover, growing awareness of Open Science and FAIR practices have resulted in more succinct focus on archiving and safeguarding the material and resources research is based on, to ensure that the production of knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable. However, as these additional research outputs have such diverse formats and ways to access, they do not always provide sufficient overview and guidance for (re)use within SSH and CH fields.

3 Creating a unified data catalogue

As part of the Werk aan Uitvoering program, two institutes bridging the worlds of SSH research and the heritage sector have therefore teamed up. The Huygens and Meertens Institutes of the KNAW, are working on a shared public facing data platform, the so-called data catalogue. Both institutes have extensive experience in making historical and current sources more accessible and are dedicated to connecting (research) data collections to ensure new opportunities for research and storytelling. At the same time, the digital processing of data at the institutes has not always been approached in a comparable manner. Though research topics may seem similar at first glance, the different research fields have developed their own unique ways of working with sources building upon longstanding traditions. The resources therefore span field notes, thesauri, audio interviews, enriched archival pieces, surveys, ground truths, TEI encoded editions, letter collections, biographical profiles, diaries, structured datasets, shiplogs, and many more.

To create a unified point of access for these complex and heterogeneous datasets that serves both the established users and the more diverse audiences we aim to reach, many considerations needed to be taken into account. For example, the metadata models and registries currently in use do not provide space for an adequate description of complex contextual elements that are essential for responsible (re)use, such as the inherent biases due to cultural and historical influences on production. In the project, we therefore work on extracting, restructuring and enriching this contextual information as an integral part of workflows to aid interoperability. Once this information is well organized and presented, it will become more accessible for exploration, (re) use, research, and understanding.

4 From user studies to prototype and back

In order to get an insight into the (potential) user groups of the data catalogue, we hosted a micro survey on the Huygens and Meertens websites.⁽⁵⁾ The goal was to get an idea of the types of users who visit the websites and their motivations.⁵ After a

⁴ These methods of knowledge utilization are becoming more acknowledged and encouraged in policies, e.g. the Recognition and Rewards research policy of the NWO <https://www.nwo.nl/en/recognition-and-rewards>

⁵ This work also builds upon earlier experience within the Oorlog voor de Rechter project (1) and the Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed research on user profiles for digital heritage(2) (6) .

few broad questions, we asked whether they ever made use of databases or datasets, and if so, followed up with questions about their specific needs and requirements. We also asked the respondents whether they wanted to participate in a follow-up interview to gather more in-depth insights. In total 498 people filled in the survey and 38 volunteered for an interview. We simultaneously started the first of two design sprints in order to develop a prototype for the data catalogue. This development was informed by both previous user research and the results of the micro survey. The user studies gave us the insights needed to focus these short and intense sprints. For example, our users indicated they need a clear presentation of basic metadata of a dataset and want full-text search options to search through sets. We then put the design prototype of the data catalogue to the test during the in-depth interviews. Results from these interviews helped hone in further on the key requirements of users, and how best to present and structure information to facilitate reuse of datasets and creation of new research and stories.

5 Insights in ongoing research

The authors will present the latest developments of the ongoing project and discuss the steps taken to develop a user-friendly data catalogue. In particular we address the following questions: How did we conduct user studies and align their needs and motivations with the design and technical functionalities of the data catalogue? How can standardized layers of visualization and meta-data contextualization, such as the data-envelopes established at the Huygens institute (3), help tell new stories with these datasets? What are the domain specific considerations that have shaped our work and what role does design play in allowing our sources to reach wider audiences? And lastly, which methods of visualization could aid in providing insight into what is on offer?

References

- [1] L. Baltussen. Trefwoorden en tranen in het grootste oorlogsarchief van nederland. *Huygens Institute*, 2026.
- [2] Astrid de Beer, Dasha Maskalenko, Hannah Jansen, Henriette Kosse-Ruinen, Iris Brandts, Kees Hendriks, Luud de Brouwer, Vincent de Keijzer, Lotte Baltussen, Sophie Heijkoop, and Maurits van der Graaf. *Gedragsprofielen Digitaal Erfgoed - Functionele Specificaties (1.0)*. Zenodo, 2021.
- [3] Mrinalini Luthra and Maria Eskevich. Data-envelopes for cultural heritage: Going beyond datasheets. In Ingo Siegert and Khalid Choukri, editors, *Proceedings of the Workshop on Legal and Ethical Issues in Human Language Technologies @ LREC-COLING 2024*, pages 52–65, Torino, Italia, May 2024. ELRA and ICCL.
- [4] E. Meijers. Van data naar dienst. visie op de ontwikkeling van verbonden erfgoed-diensten (1.0). *Zenodo*, 2025.
- [5] C. Rohrer. When to use which user-experience research methods. *nngroup*, 2022.
- [6] M. Verloop. *Zoek, beleef, creëer en bewonder. Gids voor het werken met acht gedragsprofielen digitaal erfgoed (1.0)*. Zenodo, 2025.